

Numerical and experimental analysis for mode I fracture of Ti/APC-2 hybrid composite laminate

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ABSTRACT

Fracture Behavior Analysis of a hybrid laminate made of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (APC-2) and metal foil plies (titanium) was evaluated by the combination of an experimental method of double-cantilever-beam (DCB) and the finite element method. The critical loads P_C and energy release rates were obtained from DCB experiment. The complex stress intensity factor was computed using the definition of complex stress intensity factor. The research found the K-dominant zone existed near the crack tip which proved the reliability of stress intensity factor. The energy release rates and stress intensity factors of Ti-PEEK with untreated titanium alloys and sandblasted titanium alloys were compared in this paper. The influence of surface treatment of titanium alloys on Ti-PEEK adhesive strength was preliminarily explored.

1. Introduction

Fibre metal hybrid laminate is a kind of advanced composite used on airplanes. It has little weight and high fatigue resistance compared to single metal and can be processed easily like conventional metal alloy sheets compared to fiber-reinforced plastic. The laminate combined the excellent impact toughness and fracture toughness from the metal and high modulus and strength from composite^[1]. Fibre metal hybrid laminate has developed through ARALL, GLARE, CARALL, TiGr and the Ti/APC-2 hybrid composite laminate has better properties following the fourth generation development^[2]. A good condition in the interface between metal sheet and composite is the key factor which influenced the mechanical properties of the fibre metal hybrid laminate, even deciding if the laminate can be put into application. The bonding strength of metal and composite was decided by their wettability and interface morphology. The better wettability and higher interface toughness can be beneficial to the interface bonding strength. Now the measurement to estimate the bonding strength can't systematically explain the interfacial behavior of fibre metal laminate, for example the common Lap test. Now fracture toughness based on fracture mechanics to estimate the interfacial bonding strength is achieved by researchers around the world. Glyn lawcock, Lin Ye^[3] use the DCB experiment to calculate the energy release rate of metal fibre laminate, moreover influence on the fracture toughness, tensile strength and shear strength by different metal surface finish is analyzed. Cantwell^[4] use the SCB experiment to calculate the I and II energy release rates. A series of typical load-deflection curves and energy release rates of different crack propagation are achieved. X H Zhang, Y H Li^[5] use the finite element method to analyze the functionally graded materials with cracks perpendicular to the gradient direction.

The influence on the crack tip stress intensity factor, strain energy density and crack propagation angle by Gradient distribution index under the mechanical load and the therm load is also researched. However, there is no accurate standard method to estimate the fracture behavior of the fibre metal laminate therefore the standards and methods for evaluating the fracture behavior is very important. The paper combined the DCB experiment and the finite method to analyze the fracture behavior of Ti/APC-2 hybrid composite laminate, the Fracture toughness: stress intensity factor and energy release rate were calculated.

2. Experimental program

2.1 DCB experiment specimen

The 2/1 structure Ti/APC-2 laminate used for experiment was made of two titanium alloy sheets, one prepreg APC-2 and six peek membranes. The Layer direction of unidirectional prepreg is 0° . The dimension of sample was $180\text{mm}\times 25\text{mm}\times 0.8\text{mm}$. There were two solutions for titanium alloy; no surface treatment and sand blast treatment. The procedure for specimen preparation was listed as follow: first, the titanium alloy and prepreg with the area of $180\text{mm}\times 25\text{mm}\times 0.8\text{mm}$ and aluminum film(used for pre-crack) with area of $50\text{mm}\times 25\text{mm}$ were cut out. Second, dipped into acetone and cleaned, the lay-up as the figure1 shown was put into mold. In order to avoid the adhesive by PEEK, the aluminum film was used for separate from the mold and laminate. Last, took the mold into press vulcanizer, heated to 390°C , kept the heat preservation for 20 min, pressed 0.6 MPa, took out after naturally cooling to room temperature.

The prepared specimens were attached on one inch of the hinges by 3M glue, curried for 12 hours at room temperature. The figure 2.1 showed the specific specimens.

Figure2.1 the specific specimens

2.2 DCB experiment

The experiment was implemented through self-control fixture and SANS microcomputer control electron universal testing machine and the detailed equipment was shown as the figure 2.2. The procedure was accord with the HB7402-96, controlled by displacement, loaded by the 1-2mm/min velocity. First step distance was 20mm, the follow steps distances were 10mm until the length of crack achieved 100mm. After every step, it was needed to unload until the end of the experiment.

During the procedure, balanced load on the hinges should be certified and the accurate crack growth should be observed firstly. In order to record the every crack length, the correction fluid was used to paint on the thickness direction of laminate. The load-deflection curve was used to record the critical crack growth load, the distance of load point and the crack length.

Figure 2.2 DCB experiment facility

After the experiment; some phenomenon was summarized as the follow; the first crack growth step was higher the after ones; the load increased to the critical load then rapidly fell down. The critical load was decreased after the first step; the residual deflection is very little. Figure 2.3 and 2.4 showed the load-deflection curves on the two kinds of laminates.

Figure 2.3 the load-deflection curves (no treatment on titanium alloy surface)

Figure 2.4 the load-deflection curves(sand blast on the titanium alloy surface)

2.3 the strain-stress distribution of crack tip

As the dispersal coefficient of every crack critical load, the stain-stress distribution of every step will be calculated by the finite element method. As the residual deflection is small, the 1/4 node method based on linear elasticity fracture mechanic was used to simulated the crack growth.

Table 3.1 the property of the titanium alloy and PEEK

	Elastic Modulus /GPa	Poisson's ratio
titanium alloy (TA2)	116	0.34
adhesive lay (PEEK)	3.7	0.4

Table 3.1 showed the property of the titanium alloy and PEEK, figure 3.1 and 3.2 showed the the stain-stress distribution of laminate by the finite element method, figure 3.1 showed the tensile stress and figure 3.2 showed the shear stress. From the picture the stress around the crack tip is very high. The irregularity of the stain-stress distribution was existed.

Figure2.4 tensile stress distribution

Figure 2.5 shear stress distribution

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 energy release rate

The energy release rate was calculated by the national standards HB7402-96, the formula for energy release rate was showed as the follow;

$$G_{IC} = \frac{mP\delta}{2Wa} \times 10^3 \quad (3-1)$$

G_{IC} –mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, J/m^2 ;

m –flexibility coefficient;

P –the load of critical point, N;

δ - the distance of critical point, mm;

W –the reathth of specimen, mm;

A – the length of crack, mm;

The energy release rate of two kinds of laminate for every step was calculated by the DCB experiment. The energy release rate of laminate with the sand blast treatment on the titanium surface is higher than the one with no surface treatment obviously. The result explained that the sand blast on titanium alloy surface can enhance the energy release rate of the Ti-PEEK and the bonding strength.

Figure 3.1 the energy release rate of every step

Through three specimens, the calculated results were essentially identical which can prove their reliability. The table 3.2 showed the average energy release rate of the two kinds of laminates.

Table 3.2 the energy release rate

	Laminate with no surface treatment	Laminate with sand blast treatment
$G_{IC}/(J/m^2)$	122.67	155.34

3.2 mixed mode stress intensity factor

The critical load was achieved by the DCB experiment and the stress-strain distribution was calculated by the finite element method. The measurement for the irregularity is the stress intensity factor. The paper will obtain the stress intensity factor by the stress-strain distribution, however as the difference between two materials, the interfacial fracture behavior become more complex^[6]. There were not only normal stress but also shear stress existing in the experiment. Therefore mode I and II will coupled together.

The paper used the stress method to achieve the mix mode stress intensity factor^[7-9], the formula 3.1 showed the solution formulas.

$$K_I = \sqrt{2\pi r} [\tau_{xy} \sin(\varepsilon \ln r) + \sigma_y \cos(\varepsilon \ln r)] \quad (3-1)$$

$$K_{II} = \sqrt{2\pi r} [\tau_{xy} \cos(\varepsilon \ln r) - \sigma_y \sin(\varepsilon \ln r)] \quad (3-2)$$

the phase angle:

$$\varphi \approx \tan^{-1} \frac{K_{II}}{K_I} \quad (3-3)$$

σ_y -the normal stress perpendicular to the interface; τ_{xy} -shear stress; I and θ -system of polar coordinates; ε -oscillating coefficient.

Three points on the crack tip was took out to calculate the stress intensity factor. As the r is very small, the accurate stress intensity factor will be achieved by the Lagrange's interpolation.

$$K_I \Big|_{r=0} = \frac{r_B r_C \cdot K_{IA}}{(r_A - r_B)(r_A - r_C)} + \frac{r_A r_C \cdot K_{IB}}{(r_B - r_A)(r_B - r_C)} + \frac{r_A r_B \cdot K_{IC}}{(r_C - r_A)(r_C - r_B)} \quad (3-4)$$

$$K_{II} \Big|_{r=0} = \frac{r_B r_C \cdot K_{IIA}}{(r_A - r_B)(r_A - r_C)} + \frac{r_A r_C \cdot K_{IIB}}{(r_B - r_A)(r_B - r_C)} + \frac{r_A r_B \cdot K_{IIC}}{(r_C - r_A)(r_C - r_B)} \quad (3-5)$$

In summary, the mixed mode stress intensity will be obtained as the figure 3.2 and 3.3.

Figure 3.2 the stress intensity factor of the laminate with no surface treatment

Figure 3.3 the stress intensity factor of the laminate with sand blast treatment

As the figures shown; the mode I and II existed at the same time, the stress intensity factor was increased as the gained load. The KI and KII has the same changing trends which mainly influenced by the experiment load. The result showed that the stress intensity factor of laminate with sand blast surface treatment on titanium alloy was higher than the one with no treatment on titanium alloy which explain the sand blast surface treatment can enhance the bonding property.

Figure 3.4 and 3.5 showed the stress distribution near the crack tip, the rate of the stress and distance was linear at some extend which proved the existent of K dominant area^[10]. So the normal stress and shear stress distribution can be expressed by the formulas and the stress intensity factor can be used to estimate the interface fracture behavior.

Figure 3.4 the normal stress distribution of the crack tip

Figure 3.5 the shear stress distribution of the crack tip

4 conclusion:

(1) With the DCB experiment and finite element method, the interfacial fracture behavior was estimated deeply and the fracture toughness (energy release rate and stress intensity factor) was calculated in this paper.

(2) As the difference between the titanium and PEEK, the interfacial fracture contained fracture of both mode I and mode II. So the stress intensity factor is mixed factor. The KI and KII were calculated in this paper.

(3) The normal stress and shear stress near crack tip were taken out to prove the reliability of the stress intensity factor. As KI is proportional to the normal stress and so was KII and shear stress, the mixed stress intensity factor can be used for explanation of fracture behavior.

(4) Compared the two kinds of laminates(the one is no surface treatment on titanium, the other is sand blast treatment on titanium), the fracture toughness of the formal laminate is lower than the later one which explained that sand blast treatment on titanium surface can enhance the bonding property of laminate.

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